

**CUSP Workshop III:
Practice-based analysis of data needs, availability,
reuse and gaps for MNP-risk related tools**

Minutes

April 21, 2023, 09:00 - 13:30 CET

Welcome Address by Rudolf Reuther (Plasticsfate)

- CUSP seeks to gain new scientific insights into the microplastics problem

Summary of previous workshops from a data needs perspective by Bernd Giese (Plasticsfate)

- Workshop #1/3: Regulatory insights and knowledge gaps in February revealed that
 - There are deficits in knowledge about the risk potential; for an appropriate adaption of policy we should know more, in particular about a) the sources of MNP (here also sectoral impacts are of interest) and b) fate which means that we have to investigate the breakdown mechanisms and pathways
 - scientific evidence on human health effects still limited
 - What are the differences between types and sizes of MNP with regard to their effects? Analytical methods available?
 - Exposure: more precise estimates are necessary and also more data for food and drinking water
- Workshop #2/3: Human health risk assessment frameworks for micro- and nanoplastics in March:
 - currently from the ECHA perspective it is not possible to reliably determine thresholds for MP – and therefore they should be treated like Persistent/Bioaccumulative/Toxic or Very persistent/Very bioaccumulative substances
 - first approaches trying to build up risk assessment frameworks based on experience with nanoparticles
 - but risk assessment frameworks for nanoparticles not fully transferable to MNPs
 - non-knowledge can be reduced by grouping and data can be obtained in a structured way by integrated approaches of testing and assessment (“IATA”)

1st Session on types of data needed for tools related to risk of MNP in CUSP and beyond

Input by Andrea Haase (Polyrisk):

- consider also weathered particles and additives besides the virgin material
- depend on testing strategies to distinguish between particles of low and high concern
- hardly any data available
- nano-fraction: different behaviour regarding uptake/distribution and also effects
- Q &A:
 - for identification of tyre rubber a combination of mass based and spectroscopic techniques is used (TED-GC/MS or pyrolysis-GC/MS)
 - as markers for tire rubber are used 1-phenyl-3,4-divinyl-, (1R,3trans,4trans)-cyclohexane, (for SBR) and 3-cyclohexen-1-yl Benzene (for SBR) and 2,5,6-trimethyl-1,3,6-Heptatriene for natural rubber
 - regarding the size limit Polyrisk works with 1 µm as max, but in general work with rather polydisperse material, size-fractionated material would help

Input by Steffen Foss Hansen (Plasticheal):

- information is only available for some kinds of plastic and additives
- not clear whether the assessed tools in the end will cover all MNP risks
- in Plasticheal they start investigation from the particles
- literature review will be published, are still working on it
- database of research projects is available at their website (<https://www.plasticheal.eu/en/results>)

Input by Ivana Banic (Imptox):

- studying effects in general but focus on allergy
- use mostly data from clinical studies
- different sampling sites across the country
- samples from children (6-18 years)
- stool samples, blood samples, in a targeted subpopulation: induced sputum and exhaled breath condensate samples
- main challenges: getting data from participants, consistency in follow-up studies
- use also in-vitro tests (cytotoxicity assessed by level of mitochondrial dysfunction, immunomodulatory effects by APC uptake of MNPs)

Input by Dana Kühnel (Plasticsfate):

- there is a need for standardization of input data for risk tools (data format and quality but also generation of data)
- quality assessment approaches for the input data are necessary
- a paper on the data needs could be beneficial for the community of MNP researchers, might be an outcome of the workshop

Input by Luca Nizetto (Papillons):

- need reference materials for hazard assessment
- typically used material: mulching films (causes soil pollution)
- test also biodegradable plastics
- will soon publish catalogue of reference materials in a deliverable
- cryomilling of mulching films to obtain particles
- MNPs from mulching films may change properties of the habitat although they are too big to pass biological barriers
- also particles deposition is monitored in Papillons

Preliminary summary on data needs by Christina Hipfinger (PlasticsFatE)

- overview of the previous inputs structured along the guiding questions of the session (see slides of this summary by Christina Hipfinger):
 - What methods are you developing (or applying) for risk analysis/risk assessment?
 - What type of data are needed?
 - What sources do you use to obtain the data?
 - Are there any problems in collecting these data?

Structured discussion (breakout groups) about key requirements in terms of data

Break-out group “characterization of MNPs”, notes by Bernd Giese (Plasticsfate), Walter Ruggeri Waldman (UFSCAR, Brazil) and Christina Hipfinger (Plasticsfate):

- Context matters in the preparation of artificially weathered particles: UV-A is slower (months to years) and more representative of environmental degradation, whereas UV-C is faster (days to weeks) and less representative of environmental degradation.

- Characterization of particles 1: DSC can provide information about crystallization as a potential indicator of degradation, but it cannot be used with single particles due to the minimal mass needed.
- Characterization of particles 2: FTIR can help to distinguish between LDPE and HDPE, and can also provide important information regarding degradation status.
- FTIR: only larger particles measurable (in millimeter-scale), smaller fractions are not measurable (not even in micrometer) – can anybody help with this problem?
- Raman spectroscopy: MNPs are measurable up to one micrometer
- Weathering is an important aspect since it may change surface properties (hydrophobic may become hydrophilic)
- How to artificially weather MPs? With UV A? With UVA the plastic may erode without stabilizer!
- Some research groups lack instruments for measurements → problems accessing equipment
- The solutions discussed in this group were quite specific, there seem to be no general answers
- Important question: What are the most important characteristics for risk characterization? → What questions should we ask in particle characterization?
- Discussion mostly about size measurement, but also chemical composition

Break out group “Method standardization”, notes by Lesley Tobin (Plasticsfate) and Raymond Pieters (Polyrisk):

- (Rudolf Reuther, Plasticsfate) standardization/harmonization/validation is needed for data sharing/comparability
- (Andrea Haase, Polyrisk) standardization is a process, we have to start with in house validation and standardization, intra and interlaboratory validation necessary; finally, we should establish regulatory readiness levels
 - 1st stage: Research, definition of SOPs (at end of CUSP expected) and in-house validation/standardization, share SOPs with other labs
 - 2nd stage: Intermediate – discussion with regulatory experts. Presenting selected methods
 - 3rd stage: standardization formal validation

- Najmus Khan (Noakhali Science & Technology University, Bangladesh): There is too much scope for error and there are limitations depending on the equipment. We need different methods for different scenarios and contexts. We should use more methods and combine them.
- Damjana Drobne (Plasticsfate): We should go to standardized approach even if using different methods → Need for MNP standards/reference material
- James Johnstone: There are efforts to characterize chemical contamination risk but there is a bias towards testing of polystyrene and often its homogenous. There should be efforts to address this → we need more data on other types of plastics – particularly in terms of shapes. Needs to be agreement on ref materials that reflects our concerns (e.g., reference material of aged MNP)
- Andrea Haase: We have to agree on test materials. In the first step we may have representative test mats as the OECD did with nanomaterials. This needs to be pushed forward so that we have materials that are more harmonized. Then we can have a prioritization workshop within CUSP where each project proposes different materials that they feel are candidates. Maybe in the 4th year we can organize round robins and share sops. We can organize selected workshops e.g., with CEN or ISO where we can find out who is working on which standards and we can reach out internationally.
- Rudolf Reuther: It's a chicken-egg situation. We have CUSP inter laboratory cooperation with materials to test our methods. What comes first? Materials or Methods?
- James Johnstone: If you have to modify the protocols, it can affect the results.
- Raymond Pieters: We are still struggling with in vitro and it's a challenge. But if you have a few particles then at least we have a starting point. But we should also consider applicability domain. Not all particles can be tested in the same way. Some are very difficult to test in vitro.
- Raymond Pieters: Good reporting is paramount. Data must be annotated with metadata. Method selection, measured endpoints etc. are covered but the details are often missing. We should include as much info as possible to increase the usability of what we are doing. How can this be done better to make our output reusable?
- James Johnstone: Consider also contamination, also as result of extraction. How do we prevent contamination too?
- Damjana Drobne: On sharing of SOPs a workshop needed (not at the end of CUSP, but soon).

Break out group “Complexity of MNP problems”, notes by Esther Lenssen (Polyrisk):

- Julia Catalán (Plasticheal): How to characterize a mixture of particulate material, chemicals and potential contaminants?
- Stepwise approach to look at contaminants, biological agents. Comprehensive analysis of several contaminants and adjuvants is not possible.
- Pieter van Broekhuizen: Would you include the vector function of MNP as subject for discussion as well?
- This is part of the ImpTox project (MNP as a-biotic and biotic adjuvants, e.g. heavy metals).
- Nanoparticles in air cabins of aircrafts. Airotax syndrome. Affector function is essential element of risk assessment. Look on whole background on mixture of particles. Carrier function (both during manufacturing and acquired along the way) will have major influence on exposure.
- Julia Catalán: Approach of complex mixtures when considering risk assessment.
- High influence of e.g. metals is very high correlated with MNP exposure. Is there a mixture approach in vitro/ in vivo to get more info on mechanistic information?
- Dana Kühnel (Plasticsfate): For the development of the risk evaluation tools, they consider in the design the presence of plastic associated chemicals (not only additives, degradation products of aging, chemicals that attach during life cycle). However, analysis is at the moment focused on analyzing polymers/MNPs, not so much additives. Too early for now. Therefore, take more stepwise approach.
- Anita Jemec Kokalj (Plasticsfate): Chemical additives were also analyzed in MNPs. Very few effects observed of leachates. Concentrations of leaching were always very low. Difficult to test what the contribution is, but at the moment it seems the leachates don't have an additional effect. (no conclusions just yet on chemical contributions next to particle effect).
- Nerea Portillo (University of Trento, Italy): Are there any insight/works in how MP attach to sediment or degrade in water environments therefore impacting aquatic ecosystem?
- UMZ are preparing sampling campaign in Aruba, which will be analyzed for MNPs, across different sampling points at the river. No results just yet. Unclear whether they will be able to evaluate degradation process of MNPs.
- See also the paper on biodegradation tests by Anita Jemec Kokalj.
- Malay: As a risk assessor of human health, I am keen to know how to determine

- 1) Trend in toxicity related to particle size as we move from nano ranges to micro ranges
- 2) Can toxicity data generated on pristine NP/MP be used for risk assessment given the vector nature of these particles?
- Pieter van Broekhuizen: Reference to the published article on tyres (in this publication there is also a reference to the background reference document):
 - van Broekhuizen P, Säämänen A, Schuurbijs D, Isigonis P, Jensen KA, Kühnel D and Le Blansch K (2022), Tyre wear nanoparticles as test for a nano risk governance framework. *Front. Environ. Sci.* 10:1045246. doi: 10.3389/fenvs.2022.1045246
 - van Broekhuizen, P. (2022). Case study rubber tyres – airborne release of tyre wear particles. Available at https://www.researchgate.net/publication/363861725_Airborne_release_of_tyre_wear_particles_NanoRigo_2022.doi:10.13140/RG.2.2.17576.24329

2nd Session on data sources and data processing for risk related tools

Study quality assessment approach,
presentation by Anita Jemec Kokalj (University of Ljubljana)

- list of criteria designed specifically for nano and microplastics is based on toxicological studies. An amazing observation was, that PS-MNPs usually have a lot of impurities that might trigger additional toxicological effects, but only very few tox-studies consider these impurities → there is still a lot of work to do in order to estimate the toxicological hazard-potential.
- Question from the audience: are there also recommendations for specific laboratory techniques on how the data can be obtained in the laboratory?

→ Anita: No, the list only contains enumerations of important issues to consider; the list does not deal with laboratory techniques. For laboratory techniques, Anita recommended the “Nanocret”-approach, that deals with issues such as how the data can be obtained in the laboratory.

- Question from the audience: on what basis did you evaluate the reference of your criteria (“voluntary“, “desirable“, “mandatory“)?
→ Anita: for example, if publications report about “chemicals having an important effect“, this issue was evaluated by “mandatory”

Introduction to data sources/eNanoMapper, types and definitions of data,
presentation by Nina Jeliaskova (IDEAconsult Ltd)

- The e-nanomapper is already used in more than 20 projects so far
- Question from the audience (Dana Kühnel): is your presented program automatically inserted into the e-nanomapper?
→ Nina: No, data are inserted via the dossier.
- Question from the audience (Dana Kühnel): can you explain the approaches of the automatic quality rating in more detail?
→ Nina: There are a few approaches.
Nina will send some papers about it.

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE STEPS

- Bernd Giese: The organizers of this workshop are going to make the slides of the presentations available and provide a short summary report/minutes.
- There is also the idea of a publication that addresses the results of this workshop → Dana Kühnel had an idea for the title of this publication and quoted Steffen Foss-Hansen's "a wish list of data".
- Another idea, proposed by Damjana Drobne: A follow-up workshop at the end of the CUSP-projects. Then, we might recognize if there have already been made some progress in any of the issues and problems that we've discussed within this workshop today.